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STUDY OF THE EFFECT OF IONIC AND NON-IONIC SURFACTANTS AS PERMEATION ENHANCERS ON METFORMIN TABLETS

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ABSTRACT

Metformin, a BCS class III drug has low bioavailability because of its low permeability through the gastrointestinal tract. The low permeability is due to its less lipophilicity. The objective of present investigation to enhance the intestinal permeability of metformin by using ionic and non-ionic surfactants such as sodium lauryl sulphate (SLS), sodium dodecyl sulphate (SDS), TWEEN 80 & SPAN 40. Ionic surfactant acts as better permeation enhancers than non ionic surfactant. The permeation of drug was measured by everted sac technique using chicken intestine. The drug was absorbed through chicken intestine mainly by passive diffusion mechanism. The order of permeation enhancement activity of surfactants is SLS>SDS> TWEEN 80> SPAN 40. Permeation of drug:SLS, 1:0.3 ratio found to be high than compared to other ratios and surfactants. Selected surfactant ratio with other additives compressed into tablets. The pre and post compression parameters like bulk density, angle of repose, hardness, friability, weight variation, drug content, disintegration time and all the parameters were within the acceptable limits. The effective drug permeability (P_{eff}) values selected formulation (FTA3) higher than commercial tablet by using SLS as a permeation enhancer improved the permeability. Therefore, FTA3 formulation was more permeation through the mucous membrane of the chicken intestine.

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INTRODUCTION

A great number of currently available drugs fall under the class III of the biopharmaceutical classifications system, possess high therapeutic potential but cannot be delivered by oral route because of its poor permeation across the GI epithelia. Drugs have low intrinsic membrane permeability, probably because of their low lipophilicity and zwitterion character at physiological pH or substrate to drug efflux pumps like p-glycoprotein, ionic charge and high molecular weight.

Metformin is a biguanide antihyperglycemic agent used for treating non-insulin-dependent diabetes mellitus (NIDDM), is a BCS class III drug. Metformin has low bioavailability orally 50-60%.¹ owing to its very less permeation through GI epithelia. The low permeability of metformin is due to its low lipophilicity. One method to improve the permeability of metformin is by the use of permeation enhancers. By increasing the lipophilicity of the metformin we can increase the permeability of metformin through the GI epithelia.²

For this study intestinal absorption (permeability) studies are to be performed. These studies based on isolated intestinal sacs are routinely performed. To the best of our knowledge *in vitro* absorption studies using chicken intestine have less frequently used.³ So, in the present work chicken's small intestine was used for intestinal absorption studies of prepared tablets based on the assumption that membrane permeability of drugs is not species dependent since the composition of plasma membrane of intestinal epithelial cells is similar across the species.^{4,5}

The aim of the present investigation was to enhance the intestinal permeability of metformin by using ionic and non-ionic surfactants as permeation enhancers. To study the effect of surfactants of different ratios on drug permeation. Then select the molar ratio of drug and surfactant at which maximum increase in partition coefficient. Selected formulation compared with marketed formulation (CTAB) for *in-vitro* permeability studies. .

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Metformin was obtained as a gift sample from Orchid pharmaceuticals, INDIA. Sodium lauryl sulphate, Micro crystalline cellulose, Dicalcium phosphate, Cab-O-Sil, Magnesium stearate, was procured from commercial sources. All the chemicals and solvents used were of analytical grade.

Analytical method for the estimation of metformin:

Preparation of Standard solution:

Standard solutions of various concentrations of metformin were prepared from secondary stock solution (100 µg/mL) using phosphate buffer pH 7.4 i.e., 2, 4, 6, 8, and 10 µg/ml solutions. The absorbances of dilutions were determined at 232nm using UV-Visible spectrophotometer.

Procedure for determination of partition coefficient ($k_{o/w}$):

The partition coefficients of metformin with or without permeation enhancers in different molar ratio were determined between 7.4 pH phosphate buffer and n-octanol.

Method of determination:

n-octanol (10mL) and phosphate buffer 7.4 pH (10mL) were taken in to a 100mL conical flask. These two phases were saturated with each other for 24 hours. Metformin (50 mg) was weighed accurately. It was added carefully to the saturated solution. The conical flask was kept for shaking on a rotary shaker for 24 hours at room temperature. The obtained solution was transferred in to a separating funnel and kept undisturbed for an hour. The two solvents were separately collected in to test tubes and the drug content was analyzed spectrophotometrically at 232 nm in both the solvents.

Then the partition coefficient ($k_{o/b}$) is determined by substituting the concentrations of metformin in n-octanol and phosphate buffer 7.4 pH in the following equation. The partitioning coefficient was calculated using the following equation:

$$K_{o/b} = a_o / a_b$$

Where a_o and a_b are the concentrations of the drug in n-octanol and buffer respectively.

Procedure for optimization:

The partition coefficient of metformin alone was determined from the above procedure.

1. Partition coefficient of the drug with permeation enhancers (Sodium lauryl sulphate, Sodium dodecyl sulphate, Polysorbitate (Span40), Tween80) at different concentrations are determined and the concentrations which showed maximum increase in Partition coefficient of metformin was selected for further study.
2. The concentrations of ionic and non ionic surfactants which showed maximum increase in Partition coefficient of metformin was used in combination and the increase in Partition coefficient by the above mixture was determined.
3. Comparison of partition coefficients of individual concentration and mixed concentrations and the concentration which showed maximum increase in Partition coefficient of metformin was selected for further study.

Precompression studies:

Flow properties of the powders are important parameter in formulation of tablets. The flow properties of the powder of pure drug and blend of pure drug were evaluated by using parameters like Angle of repose, Carr's index and Hausner ratio.⁶

Preparation of absorption enhanced metformin tablets

Metformin tablets were prepared by direct compression method by selected ratio of permeation enhancer as given in Table 1. All the ingredients were weighed accurately and passed through sieve #40. Required quantity of metformin was added to the above mixture and all ingredients were mixed in geometrical ratio in polythene bag. Finally the magnesium stearate was added and mixed thoroughly to get free flowing powder.

Table 1- Formula of absorption enhancer metformin tablets (FTA3).

INGREDIENTS	QUANTITY (mg)
Metformin	250
Sodium lauryl sulphate	75
Micro crystalline cellulose	29
Dicalcium phosphate	29
Cab-O-Sil	4
Magnesium stearate	13

Procedure for tablet compression:

The final blend was directly compressed into tablets on a 16 station rotary tablet punching machine using 8mm tablet punch.

Post compression parameters:

The prepared absorption enhancer metformin tablets were evaluated for hardness, friability, and uniformity of weight, drug content, disintegration time and absorption studies.

Absorption studies:

Isolation of Everted Intestine:

Male white Leghorn chicks weighing between 500 and 600 g were bought from the local market. The Krebs–Ringer solution was prepared by combining 6.3 g NaCl, 0.35 g KCl, 0.14 g CaCl₂, 0.16 g KH₂PO₄, 0.15 g MgSO₄·7 H₂O, 2.1 g NaHCO₃ and 5 g glucose in one liter of distilled water. For isolation of everted intestine, the chicks were slaughtered, a median incision of the abdomen was performed, and the small intestine was freed. The lumen was carefully cleared from mucus by rinsing with a pH 7.4 buffer solution (Krebs–Ringer solution). An intestinal segment of the first 6-cm length was removed and transferred to oxygenated Krebs–Ringer solution. It was washed thoroughly with warm Krebs–Ringer solution.⁷ The proximal extremity of the intestine was turned back and ligated on a glass rod to form an everted bag.

Design of Continuous Dissolution–Absorption System Using Everted Intestine Segment

The *in vitro* continuous dissolution–absorption system design is illustrated in Figure 1. The system consisted of USP dissolution Apparatus 1 and a side-by-side perfusion apparatus holding isolated everted intestine segment. In this system, drug dissolution from the slow release tablet and permeation across everted intestine occurred simultaneously. The dissolution medium used was 1000 mL of distilled water maintained at 37 ± 0.5 °C. The perfusion apparatus consisted of two glass tubes, A and B, connected together. Tube B had a bent cannula at its lower end, and tube A, a straight cannula at its lower end. The distance between the two cannula was kept constant. The isolated everted intestinal segment was fixed between the ends of tubes A and B as shown in the Figure 1. The ends of the intestine were tied in position with a thread. The apparatus was immersed completely into the dissolution vessel.

1. Dissolution flask
2. Rotating shaft
3. Dissolution medium
4. Basket
5. Tablet
6. Oxygen tube
7. Tube A
8. Tube B
9. Everted intestine
- I. Dissolution – absorption system
- II. Absorption (perfusion) apparatus

Figure1-Design of continuous dissolution–absorption using isolated everted intestine system.

Procedure for Absorption Studies in the Continuous Dissolution–Absorption System:

In the proposed design of a continuous dissolution–absorption system, sampling can be done simultaneously for measurement of the *in vitro* dissolution and absorption profiles of the drug. The dissolution–absorption studies were performed in two parts. In the first part of study, a marketed, slow-release tablet of metformin was used. The dissolution medium consisted of 1000 mL distilled water maintained at 37 ± 0.5 °C. A fresh intestinal segment was clamped to the perfusion apparatus. The total volume of the absorption compartment (tube A and tube B of perfusion apparatus) was 35 mL of Krebs–Ringer solution. The drug diffused from dissolution medium (mucosal side) to the serosal side (absorption compartment). The formulated and marketed tablets were transferred to the dissolution basket of the designed system.⁸⁻¹² The tablet was rotated at 75 rpm speed. Dissolution samples (3 mL) were withdrawn at preselected time interval up to 2 hours. The dissolution samples were taken with replacement at 10, 20, 30, 40, 50, 60, 90, 120 and 180 minutes and the released metformin was determined spectrophotometrically at 232 nm. The transported drug from the absorption compartment was sampled with replacement (Krebs–Ringer solution) at 13, 23, 33, 43, 53, 63, 93, 123 and 183 minutes and analyzed spectrophotometrically for transported metformin at 232 nm. To allow time for drug to circulate from the dissolution vessel to the everted intestine surface, absorption samples were collected 3 min later than their corresponding dissolution samples. The whole experiment was repeated in triplicate (n=3) using fresh dissolution medium as well as fresh intestinal segment each time. The effective drug permeability (P_{eff}) across the membrane was calculated from the formula:

$$P_{\text{eff}} = \frac{dm}{dt} / AC$$

Where, dm is the drug accumulation in the absorption compartment during time interval dt
Amount of drug traversing the tissue in time t

A=Exposed area of tissue

C= Concentration of drug in donor compartment

Enhancement ratio (ER) was determined from the formula,

$$\text{Enhancement ratio} = \frac{\text{Amount of drug permeated with permeation enhancer}}{\text{Amount of drug permeated without permeation enhancer}}$$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Construction of calibration curve for metformin

A calibration curve was constructed by plotting the absorbance against the concentration ($\mu\text{g/mL}$) of metformin. The regression equation was derived from the plot. The degree of linear relationship correlation coefficient (r) was calculated and found to be 0.9994 at range of 2-10 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ indicating a positive correlation between the concentration of Metformin and the corresponding absorbance values. The regression line describing the relation between concentration and absorbance was as follows. $y = 0.057x + 0.029$.

Where, Y is the absorbance at 232nm and X is the concentration of metformin in $\mu\text{g/ml}$ as given in Figure 2.

Figure 2- Standard calibration curve for metformin.

Determine the partition coefficient of metformin:

Partition coefficient of metformin was determined and the result was tabulated in Table 2. Metformin, a hydrophilic drug containing many polar groups, exhibited low $k_{\text{oct}/\text{buffer}}$ value, 0.230. Partition coefficient of metformin with Permeation enhancers, Sodium lauryl sulphate, Sodium dodecylsulphate, Span40 and Tween80 at different molar concentrations is determined and tabulated in Tables 3, 4, 5 & 6 respectively. The molar concentration ratios of SLS and SDS, tween80 and span40 (Polysorbite) which showed maximum increase in $k_{\text{oct}/\text{buffer}}$ were 1:0.3, 1:0.4, 1:0.2, 1:0.3 and their $k_{\text{oct}/\text{buffer}}$ is 0.9516, 0.847746, 0.514234, 0.39237 with batch numbers A4, A10, A13, A18 respectively.

Among the ionic surfactants SLS has shown maximum increase in $k_{\text{oct}/\text{buffer}}$ at the molar concentration ratio 1:0.3 with batch number A4. Among the non ionic surfactants tween80 has shown maximum increase in $k_{\text{oct}/\text{buffer}}$ at the molar concentration ratio 1:0.2 with batch number A13. From this we can say that ionic surfactants have better permeation enhancing property compared to the non ionic surfactants.^{13,14} The batches of SLS and tween80 which showed maximum increase in Partition coefficient of metformin is A4 and A10, they were used in combination and Partition coefficient increase by the above combination is 0.8825, which is lesser than the maximum $k_{\text{oct}/\text{buffer}}$ attained by A4 (Table-7). This indicates the absence of additive effect. Thus, we can say that SLS at molar ratio of 1:0.3 acts as better permeation enhancer and this concentration is used for further study.

Table 2-Partition coefficient of metformin (mean \pm s.d., n=3).

S.no	Batch	Metformin: Permeation enhancer ratio	Concentration in buffer (mg/mL)	Concentration in octanol (mg/mL)	$k_{\text{oct}/\text{buffer}}$
1.	A1	1:0.0	40.626	9.38	0.230

Table 3-Partition coefficient of metformin with SLS (mean \pm s.d., n=3).

S.no	Batch	Metformin : SLS Ratio	Concentration in buffer (mg/mL)	Concentration in octanol (mg/mL)	$k_{\text{oct}/\text{buffer}}$
1.	A2	1:0.1	2.665	2.335	0.876173
2.	A3	1:0.2	2.632	2.368	0.899696
3.	A4	1:0.3	2.562	2.438	0.95163
4.	A5	1:0.4	2.734	2.266	0.828822
5.	A6	1:0.5	2.8	2.2	0.785714

Table 4-Partition coefficient of metformin with SDS (mean \pm s.d., n=3).

S.no	Batch	Metformin: SDS Ratio	Concentration in buffer (mg/mL)	Concentration in octanol (mg/mL)	$k_{\text{oct/buffer}}$
1.	A7	1:0.1	2.986	2.014	0.674481
2.	A8	1:0.2	2.917	2.083	0.71409
3.	A9	1:0.3	2.83	2.17	0.766784
4.	A10	1:0.4	2.706	2.294	0.847746
5.	A11	1:0.5	2.785	2.215	0.795332

Table 5-Partition coefficient of metformin with Tween 80 (mean \pm s.d., n=3).

S.no	Batch	Metformin: Tween 80 ratio	Concentration in buffer (mg/mL)	Concentration in octanol (mg/mL)	$k_{\text{oct/buffer}}$
1.	A12	1:0.1	3.527	1.473	0.417635
2.	A13	1:0.2	3.302	1.698	0.514234
3.	A14	1:0.3	3.376	1.624	0.481043
4.	A15	1:0.4	3.412	1.588	0.465416

Table 6-Partition coefficient of metformin with Span 40 (mean \pm s.d., n=3).

S.no	Batch	Metformin: Span 40 ratio	Concentration in buffer (mg/mL)	Concentration in octanol (mg/mL)	$k_{\text{oct/buffer}}$
1.	A16	1:0.1	3.717	1.283	0.345171
2.	A17	1:0.2	3.659	1.341	0.366494
3.	A18	1:0.3	3.591	1.409	0.39237
4.	A19	1:0.4	3.628	1.372	0.37817
5.	A20	1:0.5	3.653	1.347	0.368738

Table 7-Partition coefficient of metformin with SLS and Tween 80 (mean \pm s.d., n=3).

S.no	Batch	Metformin SLS: Tween 80 ratio	Concentration in buffer (mg/mL)	Concentration in octanol (mg/mL)	$k_{\text{oct/buffer}}$
1.	A21	1:0.3:0.2	2.613	2.387	0.8825

Pre compression studies

Flow properties of lubricated blend were determined and values were found to be in the range of 36-40°, 21-25, and 1.19-1.25 for angle of repose, compressibility index and Hausner's ratio respectively. Results indicated that flow of the lubricated blend was found to be good and can be compressed in to tablets by direct compression and respective values of the powders are shown in the Table 8.

Table 8-Pre-compression parameters (mean \pm s.d., n=3).

Formulation code	Bulk density (gm/cm ³)	Tapped density (gm/cm ³)	Angle of repose(θ) in degrees	Compressibility Index (I)	Hausner Ratio
FTA3	0.495 \pm 0.04	0.662 \pm 0.05	36.45 \pm 0.39	23.22 \pm 0.58	1.237 \pm 0.01

Post compression parameters

The Post compression parameters like Hardness, Friability, Weight variation, Drug content, Disintegration time are shown in Table 9. Hardness of tablet formulations was measured using Monsanto hardness tester and results were found to be in the range of 4-6 Kg/cm² and are well within the acceptable limits. Friability of the tablet formulations were determined using Roche friabilator were found to be well below the acceptable limit i.e., a maximum loss of weight (from a single test or from the mean of the three tests) is not greater than 1 percent. The uniformity of weight test was carried out and all the prepared tablets passed weight variation test, as % weight variation was within the Pharmacopoeial limit 7.5%. Uniformity of Content test was carried out for tablets complied with the test as each individual content is 85 to 115 per cent of the average content. Disintegration time was determined for tablet formulations and results were within the desirable range.

Table 9-Post compression parameters (mean \pm s.d., n=3).

Formulation code	Hardness (Kg/cm ²)	Friability (%)	Uniformity of weight (mg)	Uniformity of Content (%w/w)	Disintegration time(sec)
FTA3	4.6 \pm 0.05	0.69 \pm 0.04	359.4 \pm 0.03	98.45 \pm 0.04	126 \pm 0.04
CTAB	4.5 \pm 0.04	0.78 \pm 0.06	358.3 \pm 0.04	97.43 \pm 0.05	139 \pm 0.04

Drug-polymer compatibility studies (FT-IR).

The FTIR spectra of SLS appeared at 1325.21 cm⁻¹ for the sulphuryl group (S=O stretching). FTIR spectra of Metformin shows broad peak at 3414-3200 cm⁻¹ (NH₂ stretching) and at 3000-2850 cm⁻¹ (-CH stretching).¹⁵ In the formulation of SLS and Metformin all the characteristic peaks of polymer and the drug are retained showing no significant interaction between them (Figure 3a, 3b and 3c).

Figure 3a: FTIR spectrum of Metformin.

Figure 3b: FTIR Spectrums of SLS.

Figure 3c: FTIR Spectrums of FTA3.

Dissolution and Absorption studies:

The effective drug permeability (P_{eff}) across the membrane and Enhancement ratio (Er) was calculated. The effective drug permeability (P_{eff}) values FTA3 and commercial product is shown in Table 10 and Figure 4. The effective drug permeability (P_{eff}) values of FTA3 (2.201) is higher than the P_{eff} values of commercial tablet formulation (1.546) and it infers that the SLS as permeation enhancers improved the permeability of metformin from FTA3 than commercial tablet formulation (CTAB).¹⁶ Higher enhancement ratio (ER) value 69.46 for FTA3 than commercial tablet (CTAB) given in Table 11. Therefore, FTA3 formulation was more permeation through the mucous membrane of the chicken intestine than that of CTAB.

Table 10-Effective drug permeability (P_{eff}) of prepared tablet (FTAB3) and commercial tablet (CTAB).

Sampling time (min)	Effective surface area of intestinal segment (A)	Effective permeability (P_{eff}) $P_{eff} = (dm/dt)/AC$	
		FTA3	CTAB
10	175.84	0.274	0.151
20	175.84	0.383	0.285
30	175.84	0.477	0.359
40	175.84	0.578	0.457
50	175.84	0.775	0.519
60	175.84	0.923	0.626
90	175.84	1.149	0.789
120	175.84	1.620	0.988
150	175.84	1.955	1.304
180	175.84	2.201	1.546

Figure 4. Comparison of metformin permeation through intestine of P_{eff} of FTA3 and CTAB.

Table 11-Enhancement ratio (Er).

Amount of drug permeated from FTA3 at time t (mg)	Amount of drug permeated from CTAB time t (mg)	Enhancement ratio (Er)
69.46	52.27	1.32

Drug release studies:

Different release characterization model was applied on release profile, correlation coefficient (r) and release constant was calculated. Release data was analyzed as per zero order and first order models to assess the release kinetics and mechanism of drug release from the matrix tablets prepared. The coefficient (r) is used as indicator of best fitting for each of the models considered. The ' r ' values of the formulation FTA3 are higher in case of first order than zero order model (Table 12), indicating that the drug release is a concentration independent process.

Table 12- Drug release kinetics for prepared formulation FTA3.

Formulation	Zero order		First order	
	K_0	r	K_1	r
FTA3	3.45	0.986	0.086	0.993

CONCLUSION

The absorption of metformin in humans is very low according to Biopharmaceutical Classification System. This is in agreement with the permeability measurement in this study. The effect of different molar ratios of drug and surfactants (ionic and non ionic) on the partition coefficient of metformin is determined. The order of permeation enhancement activity of is SLS>SDS> Tween 80> Span 40. SLS at molar ratio of 1:0.3 Shows maximum increase in $k_{oct/buffer}$. From this study we can say that ionic surfactants have better permeation enhancing property compared to the non ionic surfactants. Flow properties of lubricated blend were determined and flow of the lubricated blend was found to be good and can be compressed in to tablets by direct compression. The post compression parameters like Hardness, Friability, Weight variation, drug content, disintegration time and all the parameters were within the acceptable limits. The effective drug permeability (P_{eff}) values FTA3 higher than commercial tablet by using SLS as a permeation enhancer improved the permeability. Therefore, FTA3 formulation was more permeation through the mucous membrane of the chicken intestine.

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